

ARCTIC PASSION

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Towards a pan-AOSS: status of cooperation with non-EU
partners and organizations

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Lead beneficiary

15 - CNR

Lead author

Vito Vitale (CNR-ISP)

Contributors

Enrico Brugnoli (CNR - IRET)

Mauro Mazzola (CNR-ISP)

Angelo Lupi (CNR-ISP)

Dissemination level

PU

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Executive Summary

In this report we analyze the state of cooperation with non-EU partners in relation to the general objective of the Arctic PASSION project to implement a pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS).

Among non EU-partners, great attention in the report is devoted to Asian partners of countries that sit as observers at the Arctic Council, considering that, in participating in this common effort, they have limitations and experience challenges similar to those faced by partners from non-Arctic European countries. Since Singapore's interest and contribution to scientific research until now has been marginal, analysis involves only 4 of the 5 Asian states sitting as observer in the Arctic Council: India, Korea, China, and Japan.

We briefly review the history of the commitment in the Arctic of those countries, following the initial steps from Japan. We also provide information for assessing the status and dynamics of the contribution they currently provide to long-term observation of the Arctic, supporting in different ways the pan-Arctic observation and scientific infrastructure development. The importance and role of the National Institutes in this effort is also highlighted.

Further, starting from this basis, we discuss the level of bilateral and multilateral cooperation, and the natural continuation of such commitments over the years. The good level of collaboration with the Arctic states is noted; however, dialogue and cooperation with the other observer states is at an early stage. The most useful platforms existing at national, regional and multilateral levels to develop the discussion on pan-AOSS design and implementation are listed and briefly described.

About North American partners, their role and commitment is obvious. We tried to identify those who could be strategic partners in a pan-AOSS perspective by a summary analysis of the dynamics that currently characterize the American and Canadian effort for long-term observation of the Arctic. Therefore, we focused on institutes, agencies and organizations, the only subjects that can ensure/support long-term commitments. They can, individually or grouped, participate in the effort of development and coordination, making use of those platforms that have also recently been developed for this purpose (see AsFF). The actions related to projects like Arctic PASSION and RNA CoObs are of great importance to support the development and bottom-up efforts of the scientific community.

The picture of the current state of cooperation and coordination, and their potential, is completed by considering the developments of last years, regarding the creation of a pan-Arctic alliance for the marine domain (ArORA). We provide a brief description of the work carried out by that initiative, and identify and describe the platforms we could use to give concreteness to the implementation of pan-AOSS in the necessary long-term perspective.

The elements collected in this way allow us to make some considerations and identify several topics/areas on which the effort could be focused in the near future.

List of Abbreviations

AAAS	American Association for Advancement of Sciences
ACE	Arctic community engagement (website)
AERC	The Arctic Environment Research Center, NIPR, Japan
ArCS	Arctic Challenge for Sustainability Project
AOS	Arctic Observing Summit
ARC	Section for Arctic Sciences (NSF-Office of Polar Programs)
ArcticNet	ArcticNet inc. is a Canadian non-profit organization
ArORA	Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance
AsFF	Arctic Science Funding Forum
ASM	Arctic Science Ministerial
ASSW	Arctic Science Summit Week
CAA	Chinese Arctic and Antarctic Administration
CAS	Chinese Academy of Sciences
CEN	Centre d'études Nordiques
CHARS	Canadian High Arctic Research Station
CIAO	China-Iceland Arctic Science Observatory
CINUK	Canada-Inuit Nunangat-United Kingdom Arctic Research Programme
CIOOS	Canadian Integrated Ocean Observing System – a GRA
CNARC	China-Nordic Arctic Research Center
DOE	US Department of Energy
EEA	European Economic Area
EGRIP	East Greenland Ice Core Project
EPB	European Polar Board
EuroGOOS	European GOOS Research Alliance
FARO	Forum of Arctic Research Operators
FIO	First Institute of Oceanography of China
G7-FSOI	The Group of seven (G7) Future of the Seas and Ocean Initiative
GINR	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources
GOOS	The Global Ocean Observing System
GRA	GOOS Regional Alliances
GRENE	Green Network of Excellence
IARC	International Arctic Research Center, University of Alaska Fairbanks
IARPC	Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee
IBCB	Ice Base Cape Baranov Station, Russia
ICARP	International Conference on Arctic Research Planning
INTERACT	International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic

JAMSTEC	Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology
KOPRI	Korean Polar Research Institute
MEXT	Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, Japan
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NCPOR	National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research, India
NIPR	National Institute of Polar Research, Japan
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NSF	National Science Foundation
NyA	NyÅlesund Research Village, Svalbard Archipelago
pan-AOSS	pan Arctic Observing System of Systems
PCSP	Polar Continental Shelf Program
PFRR	Poker Flat Research Range super site
POLAR	Polar Knowledge Canada
PRIC	Polar Research Institute of China
RADI	Institute of Remote Sensing and Digital Earth, CAS
RANNIS	Icelandic Centre for Research
RNA-CoObs	The Research Networking Activity for Coordinated Arctic Observations
ROADS	Roadmap for Arctic Observing & Data Systems
SAON	Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks
SAV	Shared Arctic Variable
SIO	Second Institute of Oceanography of China
SPA	Spasskaya Pad Scientific Forest Station
SSF	Strategic Science Fund
SST	sea surface temperature
UARCTIC	University of the Arctic
UNIS	University Centre in Svalbard
USARC	US Arctic Research Commission
US IOSS	U.S. Integrated Ocean Observing System – a GRA

1. Introduction

To achieve the ambitious goal of building a coordinated, well-integrated and sustainable pan-Arctic observation system, international cooperation is certainly fundamental. This statement, which in principle is obvious, finds substance and concreteness in the current state of measurement and research activities in the Arctic region. The strong growth of interest in the Arctic that has occurred since the late 80s has led many actors and many countries to commit increasing economic, human and infrastructural resources to research in the Arctic. In particular, long-term observation activities see many non-Arctic states significantly involved as well.

This is not surprising, since interest in the Arctic grew at the beginning mainly for scientific reasons. That the Arctic was not so remote and isolated from what was happening in the mid-latitudes had been increasingly highlighted since the late 1950s with the description of the Arctic haze phenomenon (Mitchell, 1957; Kenneth, 1985), to the point of finding traces of Arctic haze episodes up to 150 years ago (Garret and Verzella, 2008). But the idea that what happens in the Arctic is of extreme importance for the global climate system and has strong repercussions on the inhabited regions of the mid-latitudes, made its way much later, in step with understanding of the complex functioning and inter-connection of climate system components. The geopolitical and economic interest appeared only when the Arctic was identified as a precious reserve of resources still little exploited, and climate change opened new prospects for exploitation and economic development. Indeed, non-Arctic states have joined the Arctic Council only since 1998.

Figure 1 - Land super-sites operating in the Arctic at the end of the 80s (left) and at the end of 2024 (right). Consider that Alert and Ny Alesund were open only in the 80s. And the oldest site, Barrow, only opened in 1973. Orange indicates sites just opened and potentially becoming super-sites at that time (map credits: the Arctic Institute)

In terms of the pan arctic observing system (pan-AOSS), we can note the strong increase of the number of measurement sites on Arctic and sub-Arctic lands, hosting a large series of

multidisciplinary observations (Figure 1).

These infrastructures, which are often referred to as super-sites, are very important for the observation system because, thanks to the co-location of measurements related to various disciplines and various domains of the system, they are able to fully capture and highlight its complexity. In conceptual terms, we can imagine such complexity as a fifth dimension that is added to the spatial and temporal dimensions. Together with Arctic countries in North America and Europe, non-Arctic countries provide a decisive contribution to this network of super-sites and to the long-term measurement activities that are carried out in them.

Asian countries and actors are strongly involved in this effort. If we move from land to sea, the relevance and weight of Asian countries, such as Japan, Korea and China, is even stronger. Their contribution to the observation of the Arctic Ocean from the Pacific side is essential, given the vastness of the area.

When we look at the state of cooperation with non-EU partners and how to better integrate and strengthen common goals for optimal and sustainable observation of the Arctic environment, it is important to keep in mind the big difference that exists between North America and Asia. Indeed the North American component resides in the Arctic. Instead, the Asian component is comparable to the situation that European partners face, with the exception of 5 "Arctic" countries. Two aspects are relevant for non Arctic States, and different compared to the "Arctic" states:

(i) research activities, and in particular any activity that can be linked to the pan-AOSS, take place outside, and often far away, from national borders

(ii) the distance from the national territory brings with it a greater need to explain and demonstrate why it is important to invest in research in the Arctic, and why it is important to contribute to observing the Arctic, to the public and the politicians of one's own country.

In this document we aim to provide information to describe the status of cooperation and to give an account of the activities, efforts and initiatives that have been put in place within the project to promote, expand and strengthen it. While the pan Arctic perspective remains a goal we will discuss the status of cooperation with partners in North America and Asia separately.

2. Asian Arctic research: development, current landscape, infrastructures and perspectives

As already mentioned, the involvement of non-Arctic countries in the Arctic is driven by both geopolitical and scientific interests. It is always very difficult, if not impossible, to create a clear distinction between the two.

Although the interaction and interconnection between science and geopolitics has always existed, only recently has an attempt been made to look at it in a systematic way, coining the term science diplomacy. The search for a framework in which to frame this interaction conceptually has usually led to seeing either science or diplomacy as at the service of the other. Alternatively, diplomacy was meant to be informed of the progress and potential/value of science (AAAS and Royal Society, 2025). But recently a framework has been emerging in which the world of science and that of diplomacy act proactively, each impacting the other (AAAS and Royal Society, 2025). The great global challenges that we face, especially in the Arctic, make it more necessary than ever that science plays an active role in diplomacy. At the same time, policymakers and diplomats have increasingly

engaged with science over the past 20 years and play a very active role in the debate that is developing about collaboration and international science policy.

This new science diplomacy makes it possible for us to restate the scientific reasons for the commitment of non-Arctic countries in the Arctic. Such reasons are based on the environmental and climatic impact that climate change in the Arctic has at mid-latitudes. Paradoxically (for us Europeans at least), this is truer for Asian countries than for those of the Mediterranean. For example, Arctic warming can greatly impact the frequency and intensity of cold damage to East Asian terrestrial ecosystems (Kim et al., 2022). The influence of Arctic amplification, serving as the prominent feature of global warming, is very important in modulating the East Asian summer precipitation pattern, comparable to the influence of sea surface temperature (SST) (Zhang et al, 2024).

The ever-increasing awareness of this profound connection has resulted in the growth of the commitment of Asian countries in the Arctic, not experiencing the pauses and hesitations that can be seen at the European level in some cases.

The path that the scientific commitment of Asian countries, such as India, Japan, China and South Korea, have taken in the period from the beginning of the 2000s until their entry as observer states in the Arctic Council, is widely documented in the work of Stensdal (Stensdal, 2016), where it is analyzed through some significant indicators, such as funds for research and infrastructures, presence of personnel, and publications.

In terms of presence in the Arctic, from this analysis it can be seen clearly how that is concentrated on land in the Svalbard Islands, precisely in the scientific village of Ny Ålesund, where, between 2003 and 2013, the contribution of Asian partners to the overall activity started from a significant value (12% of the total researchers man-days counted in 2003), and slowly grew, reaching a stable 20-21%. As the author points out, "That increase was driven largely by heightened activity on the part of Chinese as well as Indian researchers". At sea, China, Japan and South Korea have conducted numerous scientific cruises in the period from 2008 to 2013. Before that, only in 2004 had the JAMSTEC ship Mirai undertaken an Arctic research cruise. In the case of South Korea, the cruises began after the state-of-the-art research icebreaker Araon went into service. Only India has not yet conducted any cruises in the Arctic, limiting its marine research activity with own ships to the Antarctic.

In infrastructure funding, the commitment of the four countries on which we are focusing has been significant and growing in this period. In addition to the stations at the scientific village of Ny Ålesund, we must consider the major commitment of the PRIC (Polar Research Institute of China) to build, in collaboration with the RANNIS (Icelandic Centre for Research), a joint Aurora Observatory near Akureyri: the investment was committed in 2013 and the observatory opened in 2016.

About ships, as mentioned, South Korea built a research vessel with icebreaking capabilities, the Araon, which entered into service in 2009 (Figure 2 left). Between 2012 and 2013, China also began building and constructing a second icebreaking research vessel, to be able to plan and conduct annual cruises in the Arctic in addition to the significant activity already conducted in Antarctica. The R/V Xuelong 2 (Figure 2 right), is a powerful 13,900 ton icebreaker, 122.5 meters long and 22.3 meters wide. Both vessels are capable of moving through ice up to 1.5 meters thick.

Figure 2 - KOPRI Araon (left) and PRIC Xuelong 2 (right) icebreakers.

With respect to research funding, although it is difficult to disaggregate the Arctic component from the total resources that each country dedicates to research, the strongly positive trend of resources for Arctic research in countries such as China, Japan and South Korea can be deduced from the growing interest and effort that these countries have devoted to research and in particular to environmental research. The growing interest has materialized especially in China in an ever-increasing percentage of GDP, up to 2% starting in 2012, having reached probably 2.5% by 2020. Along with greater resources for research, there has been an increase in projects and researchers involved. With respect to this topic, it is worth noting that starting in 2011, Japan has begun to aggregate most of its research efforts within a Flagship project: a large, wide-ranging initiative, financed with an adequate budget. Based on well-defined broad strategic objectives, a relatively small number of research projects (maximum around 10-11) are selected (Yamanouchi and Tanaka, 2020). The first of these projects, funded and activated by MEXT (Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technologies) for the period 2011-2016, is the Arctic Climate Change Research Project, under the Green Network of Excellence (GRENE) (*GRENE Arctic Climate Change Research Project WEB PAGE - see references*). The program development and its main results are reported in an article published in *Polar Science* in 2020 (Yamanouchi and Tanaka, 2020).

Stensdal's extensive review analysis highlights the predominant role of China and Japan in terms of scientific publications (I. Stensdal, 2016): India and South Korea only account for 17% of the scientific production related to the Arctic produced by Asian institutions. Although the contribution to Arctic Research in Asia is certainly not limited to these 4 countries, it is very reasonable to think that the contribution coming from all the other countries that adhere as members and observers to AFOPS (Asian Forum for Polar Sciences) is residual. The data collected also highlight how the scientific production of Asian researchers is very well integrated at an international level. In line with the international orientation of the polar science community, co-authorship with scientists from other countries is common. The percentage of publications that see only national authors varies from 33% in Japan, the most outward-focused, to 65% in India. In any case, scientific production is mostly addressed to journals that have good international circulation. Japan proves to be the most 'international' country with only 17% of works published in national journals, while China in this case has the highest percentage with 29%. The timeline of the publications highlights a growth for all countries in the period 2004-2013, with a trend that is very strong in China and South Korea. The data also highlights how at the beginning of the 2000s, only Japan had a well-structured Arctic research and a scientific production at least 2-3 times greater than the others.

An extensive analysis carried out by the University of Umeå within the activities carried out by the

UARCTIC Thematic Network on Research Analytics and Bibliometrics, for the period 2016 - 2022, clearly shows that this positive trend in the number of scientific products from Asian countries continues to accelerate (Aksnes et al., 2023). The absolute numbers provided by the two studies are not comparable because the counting methodology is different, but percentages and trends are. The work performed by Umeå Arctic Center also allows us to appreciate the impact that the Asian contribution has on overall scientific production. In particular, we note the great leap of China, which has now surpassed Norway's Arctic scientific production, and has reached a level not far from Canadian production. Chinese researchers, together with those from the United States and the Russian Federation, are the main responsible for the large increase (20%) in global scientific production related to the Arctic. Japan also shows constant production. In the case of Japan, it could also be interesting to analyze in detail the annual trend in relation to the introduction of the flagship project scheme as the main driving force. The publication cited contains other very interesting data about publications and especially impact.

The work and activities of the UARCTIC Thematic Network also address the funding made available for research and financed projects. The extensive analysis recently published (Aksnes et al., 2024) is especially useful to place the effort of Asian countries in the general context. The data on projects appear more reliable than that on funding, which could be affected by an underestimation of the weight and role National Institutes, and other specific channels can have in the case of Asian countries in supporting research and research infrastructures in the Arctic. Japan and China always prove to be among the 13 countries that contribute the most. And among the observer states, Japan is just behind England if we look at this parameter as an indicator.

An important aspect of the landscape of research efforts of Asian countries in the Arctic is the preponderant role that the National Polar Institutes have had in previous years, and to a large extent continue to have today. In Asian countries, interest in polar research began with the founding of a National Polar Institute. And although much of the current Arctic research in Asian countries is undertaken by scientists working at universities, research institutes and research centers, the National Polar Institutes continue to be central in the coordination of polar and Arctic research. They also act as links between the government and the research communities. In Europe, the development of polar research historically began in universities and research centers and then, over time, saw the establishment of national polar institutes. Even in nations where national polar institutes are strong and have extensive resources, this history cannot be forgotten. And even if their role is important in terms of coordination, management of infrastructures in the polar zones, definition of strategic objectives and distribution of funds, it certainly cannot be compared to that of the National Polar Institutes that were established at a time when interest in the Arctic and/or polar sciences was minimal. It must also be said that these Institutes were initially born to support research in Antarctica. This applies to the NIPR, the PRIC, NCPOR and KOPRI.

In China activities and efforts in polar research carried out by PRIC and some universities are under the coordination umbrella of the CAA (China Arctic and Antarctica Administration) in Beijing. The websites of the various Institutes provide extensive details of the infrastructure, human resources, research and tasks that they carry out.

Over time the situation has evolved, as mentioned, and little by little, new entities and Institutions have appeared with relevance on the scene; but always, in any case, in good coordination with the National Institutes.

At the moment, in Japan, JAMSTEC (Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology) and Hokkaido University are supporting the NIPR in the management of the flagship program ArCS III (The Arctic Challenge for Sustainability III) (NIPR, 2025). JAMSTEC is also managing Japan's research vessels and other sea-based research equipment, including the new icebreaker Mirai II under construction. In this Japan is different from other Asian countries.

In China, an important role for Arctic research, especially marine, is played by the First (FIO) and Second (SIO) Oceanographic Institutes, which carry out systematic cruises with their own research vessels, as well as contributing to the PRIC campaigns.

In India and Korea, the National Polar Institutes are still largely dominant, at least if we look at the aspects of observational activities and therefore at the possibility of contributing to the objective of building a pan-AOSS. In this perspective, a valuable source of information is certainly FARO (Forum of Arctic Research Operators). The material collected during the annual meetings is generally accessible from their website (FARO, 2025). Information can be found that starts in 2001. The FARO website is certainly a very valuable source of information to investigate the development of Arctic research as a whole, as well as in a regional perspective.

An aspect we would like to emphasize more, for its importance to the issue of collaboration and common effort for the development of an integrated Arctic observation system, is how, since 2011 Arctic research has been organized in Japan. As well highlighted by the work of Aksnes and others (Aksnes 2024), the Arctic research of Japan is not carried out only within the Flagship project financed by MEXT. However, it is clear that the presence of a such a large attractive center of attraction - in terms of researchers and institutions involved and economic resources available - ends up directing the Japanese contribution to the knowledge and above all the observation of the Arctic. This role as an aggregating center and the expansion of its scope from the scientific aspects to cover also management and strengthening of infrastructures, education, capacity building, and data management are well highlighted by the evolution of the structure of the Flagship project over time. It is possible to observe such evolution by consulting the various project web sites, as well as reading the two compendium project papers published in Polar Science (Yamanouchi and Tanaka, 2020; Su, 2021). Figure 3 below, where the thematic structure of the GRENE Arctic project as well as those of ArCS and ArCS II are presented, represents a schematic graphical way to appreciate that.

Figure 3 - Thematic structure of GRENE Arctic (on the top), ArCS (in the middle), and ArCS II (at the bottom) The gradually growing scope is clearly visible.

3. The status of cooperation between European and Asian partners

The previous section indicated that international collaboration is certainly among the priorities of Asian researchers and Institutes working in the Arctic.

There are two obvious reasons for that:

- (i) like all non-Arctic countries, also the Asian ones need to take advantage of the hospitality of research infrastructures and Institutions of Arctic countries;
- (ii) the experience acquired over long decades in Europe and North America are very valuable for those who start working in the same area and on the same themes.

When looking at the Arctic engagement of different Asian actors, and in particular at the aspect of cooperation, one must consider that the Asian countries' Arctic engagement and "profile" varies greatly. It is useful to look separately at the two possible cooperation modes, bilateral agreements and multilateral initiatives, considering the obvious differences in implementation and impact.

3.1. The bilateral perspective

Bilateral agreements are the obvious starting point for non Arctic countries to build and ensure their presence in the Arctic. The distribution of the Arctic super-observation sites in the 90s and up to the first years of the new millennium (Figure 1), and the favorable geopolitical condition generated by the Svalbard Treaty, explain why the first and main Arctic presence of all the Asian actors was concentrated on this archipelago, and precisely at the scientific village of Ny Ålesund. First to arrive were Japanese researchers with a station opened by NIPR in 1991, long before several European states did (Italy opened its Arctic station only in 1997). Korea, China and India established their presence and stations only over 10 years later, in 2002, 2004, and 2008 respectively.

While Japan has a much longer tradition of commitment and interest in the Arctic, China is the first player to promote collaborations that include infrastructure investments and contributions to Arctic observations outside of Svalbard.

In 2012 PRIC and RANNIS signed a framework MoU on cooperation on marine polar science and technology. And in the frame of this MoU, in 2013 they signed an agreement to build a joint Aurora Observatory in Iceland, at Karholl near Akureyri. The building and implementation of this research Infrastructure was largely supported by China. In fact, the Chinese side paid ISK 300 million (USD 2.4 million) for construction (Stensdal, 2016). The China-Iceland Arctic Science Observatory was officially opened in October 2018, but meetings of the joint science and management committee started in 2013 (Stensdal, 2016). As reported on the PRIC dedicated web page

"The China-Iceland Arctic Science Observatory (CIAO) mainly supports multi-disciplinary observation and research on aurora and space weather, atmospheric science and meteorology, biology and ecology, oceanography, glaciology, geophysics and geology, climate change and environmental science".

Despite such a broad range of activities, it is important to recall that the largest part of the interest is focused on aurora, space and physics studies. Indeed, this is also one of the main

research areas at Yellow river station in Ny Ålesund. A robust and stable source of information is the INTERACT station catalog, with the CIAO observatory being part of this network. To complete the picture, we need to consider the satellite receiving facility realized by RAD (Institute of Remote Sensing and Digital Earth) near Kiruna, Sweden. The China Remote Sensing Satellite North Polar Ground Station (CNP GS) was opened on December 15th, 2016. The large, fixed research infrastructures managed by China in the Arctic are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - *Research Infrastructure managed by Chinese Institution in the Arctic. From left to right: Yellow River Station in Ny Ålesund (Svalbard), CIAO aurora observatory (Iceland), the North Polar Ground Station located in Kiruna, Sweden*

Chinese research appears to be focused on selected priority scientific themes, such as the upper atmosphere, remote sensing observations, and glacier monitoring. In addition, China is currently the only Asian actor collaborating closely and continuously with Iceland. These elements of China's commitments highlight the differences in the involvement of Asian countries in the Arctic.

To complete the picture of bilateral cooperation for China, always only trying to focus on the research aspects and in particular those of interest for the construction and sustained support of a pan-AOSS, we note how China has entered into and/or is promoting agreements with a significant number of European Arctic actors in recent years: (i) China has its first overseas land satellite receiving station (the China Remote Sensing Satellite North Polar Ground Station cited yet above)-; (ii) with Finland, it has agreed to establish a joint research center for Arctic space observation and data sharing services, and (iii) a China–Norway Marine University Consortium Alliance was established in October 2021 with the support of the education authorities of both China and Norway (the Arctic Institute, 2020; Li and Yang, 2025). Economic and social aspects are certainly increasingly being combined with issues related to the natural system and climate change. But we return to this point in more detail in section 3.2, given that the platform that most promotes this is the China-Nordic Arctic Research Centre (CNARC). The Marine University Consortium Alliance is an example of how natural sciences and social sciences are also being integrated at a bilateral level.

As for Japan, similarly to China, the promotion of research infrastructures in the Arctic, or presence in research infrastructures of other countries, has always involved the National Institute, the NIPR. For this purpose, since June 1990 an Arctic Environment Research Center (AERC) was established within the NIPR.

Japanese research has always maintained a broad multidisciplinary spectrum, AERC

promoting very broadly Arctic research from the study of sea ice, oceanography, marine and terrestrial ecology, atmospheric sciences, glaciology, and upper atmospheric sciences in the Arctic (NIPR, AERC web page). Until 2015, in any case, activities aimed at implementing and building a long-term observation system were concentrated in Ny Ålesund. The other substantial observational activities promoted by the first flagship project for the Arctic, the GRENE Arctic project, were carried out almost entirely on the basis of measurement campaigns and research cruises limited in time (Yamanouchi and Takata, 2020 - Figure 7).

Starting in 2015, Japan also began to operate more decisively to expand its presence and its contribution to the pan-Arctic observation system on a continuous basis. AERC reorganized as the current Center to tackle more effectively Arctic issues by enhancing advanced research capability and strategic research planning. It is able, in cooperation with other institutions such as JAMSTEC and Hokkaido University, to carry out flagship programs more oriented to increasing observation capabilities and providing adequate capacity building actions. These activities ultimately require the strengthening of cooperation and the signing of agreements at different levels.

The change in this respect between the GRENE Arctic project and editions the I, II and III of the Arctic Challenge for Sustainability (ArCS) project is clearly visible in the diagrams that schematically show the structure of the projects (cfr. Figure 3).

ArCS, and then ArCS II and ArCS III, are based on the following pillars:

1. Promoting international collaborative research
2. Maintaining and developing platforms for research in the Arctic
3. Dispatching young researchers and experts to Arctic research institutions and conferences-

The above pillars are linked and reflect the vision of the Japan Arctic policy to "contribute to solve the Arctic problem with science", including in this general objective the specific one of a strategic establishment of key research and observation sites in the Arctic states. (Sueyochi et. al, 2021). But the three lines of implementation of the ArCS flagship projects can also contribute to achieving the goal of better understanding the Arctic influences on Japan, its climate, ecosystems, economy and society.

So, since 2015, a very detailed strategy has been designed and implemented, based on the plan to maintain and develop platforms for research in the Arctic region through cooperation with the Arctic states. (Sueyochi et al., 2021). The use of selected facilities is made possible by bilateral agreements between the ArCS projects and the core institutes, and the partner institutions in Arctic countries. The ArCS project included ten research and observation stations in five countries facing the Arctic Ocean (Figure 5). ArCS II consolidated what achieved during the first 5 years and moved more along long term activities (<https://www.nipr.ac.jp/arcs2/e/infrastructures/index.html>) . ArCS III, just started, will secure continuity for the next 5 years to this effort.

As stated by Sueyochi et al., (2021)

".....These stations can be broadly categorized into three groups according to the research strategy. Group A includes Arctic research stations that support new collaboration and data needs of the Japanese research community; CHARS, CEN, IBCB, EGRIP, and GINR belong to this group. Group B includes core facilities of

existing stations actively used by Japanese researchers that need to be renovated or maintained; supporting renovation or maintenance of these facilities enhances international collaborative studies; PFRR, SPA, NyA, and UNIS belong to this group. Group C includes facilities that are part of an existing framework, which was reviewed to enhance collaborative studies; IARC belongs to this group.

Figure 5 - research and observation stations in five countries facing the Arctic Ocean involved in Japan's ArCs projects

The evolution of this effort that can be learned by consulting the ArCS II web site include, in addition to sites considered between 2015-2019, Pallas in Finland and Qaanaaq-Siorapaluk Research Base in Greenland. Meanwhile, EGRIP activity was removed, probably in consideration that is a temporary activity devoted to collect ice core from the Greenland ice cap.

Thanks to ArCS projects, Japan provides a great contribution to the pan-AOSS. A solid base from which we can start for further reinforcement, better integration and coordination.

Looking at KOPRI, the strategy for structuring cooperation at a bilateral level for the Arctic as well as for the Antarctic revolves around cooperative centers (KOPRI web page). Focusing on the Arctic, the only active center is in Norway. The KOPRI-NPI Cooperative Polar Research Center was established in April 2014 at the Fram Center in Tromsø, Norway, to promote cooperation between KOPRI and the Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI). Thanks to this center, some Korean researchers (primarily from KOPRI) can spend a continuous period of 1 or 2 years in the Arctic with the aim of conducting joint research, strengthening cooperation, and learning from the exchange with an institution with long and proven experience and competence in the Arctic. From the point of view of observation infrastructures, some collaborations that include instrumentation installation are active in Canada (CHARS) and Alaska. The activities are aimed at collecting continuous data related to the atmosphere, permafrost, greenhouse gases such as CO₂ and CH₄, and vegetation state. Instrumentation

and aurora observation are also located in Kiruna (Sweden). Certainly, the major contribution of KOPRI to continuous observation in the Arctic is in the marine domain, with Araon conducting campaigns every year in the period from July to October for a duration of 80-90 days/year. It's important to note here that the policy of hosting foreign research teams, especially European teams, is very open. This applies to all three Asian countries with polar research vessels. This open strategy has been followed since the beginning by KOPRI and is the basis for the initial planning of the new Japanese icebreaker, Mirai II. But this activity obviously does not require, and is not linked to, structured cooperation agreements, the latter usually being limited to single and specific research projects.

As for India, its activity in the Arctic is mostly concentrated in Svalbard, and the only MoU for bilateral cooperation was signed with the Norwegian Polar Institute for scientific cooperation in Polar Sciences.

It is useful to point out how bilateral cooperation on scientific issues can be strongly impacted by the perception about non-Arctic actors, especially Asian ones, that politicians and public opinions in the Arctic countries can have. A study published in 2024 highlighted how research related to the aurora borealis carried out by China and Japan in the Arctic state of Iceland has been received very differently in Iceland and abroad (Ingvarsdóttir, 2024). While the Japanese research has gone almost unnoticed for decades, the Chinese research has been received with much skepticism and negative media coverage, including talk of a possible security threat. This case exemplifies the broader implications of Arctic and science diplomacy on bilateral relations. We have already reported in the previous section how in the discipline of science diplomacy a conceptual approach is gaining ground that focuses on the impacts that diplomacy can have on science and vice versa (AAAS and Royal Society, 2025).

3.2. The multilateral perspective

While bilateral cooperation can develop through dedicated meetings and workshops followed by the signing of framework agreements (usually MoUs) and/or specific agreements, multilateral cooperation needs much more time and generally roundtables/platforms that promote dialogue and the regular exchange of information about plans, funding, and perspectives. Roundtables and platforms allow for the growth of synergy between the respective strategic objectives, and in a pan-Arctic perspective, make it possible to develop plans for large-scale scientific projects and/or integrate and optimize human, economic and infrastructure resources. The goal of creating a pan-AOSS is an objective that needs to grow at this top level of roundtables/platforms to find the necessary support from agencies/institutions funding research and sustaining long term implementation efforts in the Arctic. At the same time, at bottom level, the science community works to deepen the understanding of needs, including contribution from new technologies, and to develop implementation plans, promote actions to reduce gaps, thanks to specific projects such as Arctic PASSION. The Arctic panorama does not lack these dialogue platforms. Over time, they have arisen for different reasons and because of different pressures, national, regional and international. Below, we listed some of those that were developed at national and regional level and that we consider relevant with respect to the

objective of reinforcing the cooperation with Asian partners aimed at strengthening the long-term observation system in the Arctic, reducing gaps and increasing its sustainability.

If we look at Asian countries, certainly the preponderant role of the national polar institutes is an undoubted advantage, because it reduces the number of actors with whom dialogue must be carried out. It essentially keeps to the national level the complexity and plurality of actors (institutes, agencies, universities, research centers) that this research landscape (almost any research, actually) offers.

CNARC - in the wake of an April 2012 framework agreement signed between the governments of China and Iceland to facilitate Arctic scientific cooperation, a decision was made to also develop a broader network linking Chinese and Nordic research institutions. To accomplish this objective, the **China-Nordic Arctic Research Centre (CNARC)** was founded in 2013. As stated by the CNARC web page (<https://www.cnarc.info/>)

The China-Nordic Arctic Research Center (CNARC) is an international consortium initiated by the Polar Research Institute of China (PRIC) in collaboration with respective institutes in the Nordic countries and China to promote and facilitate China-Nordic cooperation for Arctic research. CNARC provides a platform for academic cooperation with the following aims: (i) To increase awareness, understanding and knowledge of the Arctic and its global impacts. (ii) To promote cooperation for sustainable development of the Nordic Arctic and coherent development of China in the global context.

CNARC was established by 10 Institutions, four Chinese and six Nordic, which all have the capacity to influence and coordinate Arctic research. At the peak of its membership, CNARC included research centres and universities from each of the five Nordic countries. Currently, 9 Chinese and 9 European institutions are members of this consortium, mainly from Norway and Iceland. Annual conferences alternate between a city in China and one in the Nordics. CNARC is the main instrument/platform through which China develops Track II diplomacy in the Arctic. Track II diplomacy refers to sub-governmental, informal, and frequently unofficial and comprehensive diplomatic links and dialogues involving, for the most part, researchers, academics and other specialists.

ArCS e AERC - strictly speaking, both the flagship projects Arctic Challenge for Sustainability (ArCS) and the Arctic Environment Research Center (AERC) are tools created primarily to better coordinate and promote Japan's research in the Arctic. In any case, they offer a conduit for connection and dialogue with the Japanese institutions that most influence Japan's efforts in the Arctic, orienting its priorities and high-profile actions. Compared to CNAC, they are less influenced by issues and interests that are linked to sensitive goals, such as resource exploitation and economic development. Within ArCS there is a strong line of action aimed at research infrastructures.

AfoPS and EPB - are non-governmental organizations born to encourage and facilitate cooperation for the advancement of polar sciences among countries in the Asian region and Europe, respectively. The European Polar Board (EPB) was established in 1995 and has gradually grown to include 31 members from 22 European countries. The Asian Forum for

Polar Sciences (AFoPS) was established in 2004 and consists of 6 Members, national polar research institutions representing China, Japan, South Korea, India, Malaysia and Thailand. AFoPS also has 5 observers: Indonesia, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Vietnam and Pakistan. In the report to FARO for 2025, it is indicated that AFoPS started cooperation with states outside Asia, to give concreteness to the vision of a regional alliance with global perspective. Among observers are now listed also Australia, New Zealand, Turkey, Egypt and Iran.

Although in both organizations membership is seen primarily as a representation of the countries to which members belong, and at the voting level members of the same country often have the right to only 1 vote (precisely as a country), the "national" character is much more marked in AFoPS than in EPB, and this reflects the greater relevance of the national polar institutes in the Asian panorama compared to the European panorama.

The two organizations offer a unique access point to their respective communities and reference institutions. They can therefore be a valuable tool, especially to bring Asian countries closer to the complex landscape of European polar research. There is an intrinsic weakness in the current composition of AFoPS: some institutions that are gaining great weight in both Japan and China are not present at that table. As an example, consider Japan, where JAMSTEC and Hokkaido University must approach AFoPS through NIPR. From this point of view, EPB certainly appears better able to follow the dynamics that develop in the national communities, while maintaining a good degree of compactness: out of 22 countries, only 5, Italy, Finland, Norway, France and Spain, see the presence of 2 member institutions, while another 2, Belgium and Sweden, find themselves with 3 members.

4. The status of cooperation between European and North American partners

Both in the US and in Canada the landscape of cooperation between European and North American partners develops on at least 3 levels: the level of federal agencies and bodies (interagency committees, independent commissions, and collaborative networks) responsible for coordinating activities and providing strategic lines and priorities at a national level; the level of state institutions, that have a great weight especially in Canada; and, finally, the level of Academia and/or individual research institutes that, connected to the territory and populations, can have a great weight and an important specific role. In defining cooperation activities, European partners may find themselves having to and/or wanting to interact with each of these three levels according to the opportunities and needs that arise.

In addition to the level of interaction based on the bilateral model, involving partners from a single European country and partners from the US or Canada, there is also a level involving the European Union and on the other side partners from the US only, Canada only, or both countries. This level is of great importance for the development of cooperation given the large financial support that the EU provides to the polar research of its member states. At this level, institutional interlinkages between the EU, countries part of the European Economic Area (EEA), and Arctic countries have a notable impact. Figure 6 (Canova, 2023) shows, in a schematic way and through a graphic representation, the complexity of these connections. In particular, it shows how, in addition to the EU, there are several other supranational groupings that can also guide the way in which European partners can interface and collaborate with partners from the United States and Canada.

Figure 6 - EU-Arctic institutional interlinkages BEAC: Barents Euro-Arctic Council. CBSS: Council of the Baltic Sea States. EEA: European Economic Area

The state of development of the cooperation between the EU and the United States was the subject of an important conference promoted and hosted by the Wilson Center in Washington D.C., in May 2024 (Wilson Center, 2024). The meeting was not only an opportunity to present some examples of projects that involved European and American partners. Above all, it was a moment to discuss the challenges that such cooperation must be able to overcome. Indeed, it must not only improve the understanding of the changes taking place in the Arctic, but it must strengthen the flow of observations from the scientific level to the decision-making level as well. That is necessary to better inform the management/decision-making action so that it can be more effective in pursuing the well-being of the Arctic populations and promoting sustainable development.

Having said that, it is certainly important to focus on the first of the 3 levels that characterize the panorama of scientific research in the Arctic in the United States and Canada, to address the topic of cooperation as it impacts the development and, especially, the long-term support of a pan-AOSS. As a matter of fact, it is the only one with which the supranational efforts of the EU can deal. It is also the only one that can ultimately meet around the tables and on the platforms that must promote the multilateral dialogue necessary to concretely establish and maintain a pan-AOSS.

In the United States, 18 federal agencies, departments and offices support research in or about the Arctic. The Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC), established by the Arctic Research and Policy Act of 1984, is a key body for coordinating research across federal agencies. The director of the National Science Foundation serves as IARPC's chair. The web page <https://www.iarpcollaborations.org/agencies.html> provides a quick and easy gateway to learn more

about the role of each of them in Arctic research. IARPC is tasked with coordinating research planning and activities among federal agencies involved in Arctic science. In addition to this high-level coordination role, IARPC also contributes to developing bottom-level coordination of researchers. It facilitates collaboration and information sharing through the IARPC Collaborations platform, free and open to anyone who can contribute, regardless of their role in Arctic research and nationality. IARPC collaborations portal represents a very powerful tool to increasingly connect the research community in Europe and the United States and to foster cooperation and common goals from the bottom. Its use in this sense should also be discussed and promoted.

While IARPC is tasked with coordinating research planning and activities, the US Arctic Research Commission (USARC) provides recommendations to the President and Congress on Arctic research goals and policy. USARC has the function to develop and recommend an integrated national Arctic research policy and to promote cooperation among federal agencies, the state of Alaska, and international partners. Every two years, USARC delivers a report outlining recommended scientific research goals and objectives for the Arctic.

In terms of supporting long-term observation activities, the role of agencies such as NSF and NOAA is well known. At the National Science Foundation, a specific Arctic sciences section (ARC) in the Office of Polar Programs has the task of developing the Arctic research programme, also by managing Arctic research opportunities. At the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, there is no specific structure, and support for Arctic research is ensured through each of its six Line Offices, "with collaboration across offices where there are common research goals" (IARPC web page reported above). Both agencies have developed several useful tools to have a better overall picture of the effort produced and to foster collaboration. For example, a complete and updated overview of NOAA services and infrastructure in Alaska is available at <https://arctic.noaa.gov/services/>. Useful tools at the NSF include The Arctic Research Mapping Application (<https://armap.org/>), a searchable visualization tool with information about NSF-funded projects with fieldwork in the Arctic; and the Arctic Observing Viewer (<https://arcticobservingviewer.org/>), a visualization tool for observation data collected in the Arctic. In addition to NSF and NOAA, for our scopes, the activities carried out by the Department of Energy (DOE) are also of considerable importance (IARPC web page cited above).

On the Canadian front, the 3 levels indicated above are much more intertwined than in the United States, where the only Arctic state is Alaska. Roles and tasks are less defined, and the importance of the academic world and local institutions is much greater, especially in managing the infrastructures necessary for research. A fairly precise picture of what can be considered the federal/national level in Canada can be found in a report recently published by the Chief Science Advisor of Canada on emerging challenges and opportunities in Arctic and Subarctic scientific activity. The report aims to deepen/analyze the role and function that the Polar Continental Shelf Program (PCSP) has had and should have in promoting research focused on finding solutions to issues and challenges of local and global impact (right research) and research that is inclusive and involving local communities (research right) (office of the Chief Science Advisor of Canada, 2023). From this report, emerges the central role that Polar Knowledge Canada should have at a federal level for promoting the international collaboration necessary to observe and understand the complexity and interconnectedness of many of the issues the Arctic is facing.

Polar Knowledge Canada (POLAR) was created in June 2015 through the merger of the Canadian

Polar Commission and the Canadian High Arctic Research Station initiative, with the intention for it to become a hub of scientific research in the Canadian Arctic and to strengthen Canadian leadership in polar science and technology. POLAR "serves as Canada's primary point of contact with the circumpolar knowledge community," "POLAR also liaises with research organizations and institutes throughout the circumpolar world, providing guidance for multilateral scientific projects relevant to Canadian interests" (POLAR web page). These tasks are carried out by POLAR through (i) the management and development of the Canadian High Arctic Research Station (CHARS), a world-class hub for science and technology in Canada's North that complements the diverse network of research facilities across the North, and (ii) a pan-northern science and technology program, aiming to sustain POLAR's vision for a sustainable future guided by knowledge, collaboration and broad goals identified through a 5-year Science and Technology (S&T) Framework and Strategic Plan.

If POLAR is committed at the federal level to promote the development and dissemination of knowledge of the other circumpolar regions, strengthening Canada's leadership on Northern issues, and the Polar Continental Shelf Program (PCSP) represents the main instrument to provide coordinated logistical support for Arctic Research along Canada, the channel through which to discuss and develop international collaboration with the world of academia and research institutions is certainly ARCTICNET. ArcticNet inc. is a Canadian non-profit organization founded in 2003. The organization is funded mainly by the Government of Canada—initially through a program called the Network of Centres of Excellence (2003-2025). In December 2023, the Government of Canada announced that ArcticNet will be funded for the next five years in partnership with the Strategic Science Fund (SSF). ArcticNet has a large network of partnerships with 60 Indigenous organizations, 12 Canadian (federal and provincial/territorial) government agencies, 48 communities, over 40 post-secondary institutions, and research teams from over 25 collaborating countries (all information above taken from the ArcticNet web page). The annual meeting, usually held at the end of the year, offers a unique opportunity to interface with the different Canadian realities and institutions and promote high-level and wide-ranging collaborations.

A very important aspect that characterizes the development of international collaboration with partners from North America is the great relevance of the bottom-up dimension. Dialogue and interaction at the institutional level can help align scientific priorities and delivery timelines. However, the Arctic research landscape in the US and Canada is greatly fragmented in terms of the scientific community and funding sources/tools, and of the interests and priorities they need to support. Therefore, the formulation of coordinated actions for the integration and alignment of long-term observations necessarily involves work and discussion that starts at the bottom and then tries to reach the high level for continuous and adequate support. As an immediate consequence, the development strategy must necessarily pass through the search for targeted and very specific actions. Ultimately, this was the line that Arctic PASSION also tried to follow, e.g. in WP1 (see section 6.2).

Finally, there is a further aspect we would like to highlight that is also common to US and Canada and can have a great impact on the development of the cooperation between European and North American partners: the great attention to be paid to Indigenous Peoples living in the Arctic. They must be seen not only as subjects to be best served through observations and research activities, but also be actively involved from the early stages in designing and then carrying out observation activities, in co-creation, and as leaders of research in their own right. For example, the NSF Arctic community engagement (ACE) website contains information on the wide range of NSF programs,

initiatives, external collaborations and other resources that aim to facilitate effective and respectful engagement with local and Indigenous Peoples in Arctic research, education, and outreach activities. POLAR vision and strategy gives high priority on research co-conceived and co-designed with and for communities and people in the Arctic. Such a significant emphasis on the needs of populations and ecosystems in terms of sustainable development and well-being (in the one health perspective) is having a significant impact on the way in which cooperation between European and North American partners tends to develop today. In this context, the CINUK programme is certainly of considerable importance. The Canada-Inuit Nunangat-United Kingdom Arctic Research Programme aims to bring together research institutions and scientific communities from the United Kingdom and Canada to develop and implement a research programme that aligns with the National Inuit Strategy on Research objectives and actions. All projects funded by this programme therefore have representation from multiple disciplines of research, including environmental, social, cultural, health, design and engineering. The 13 projects funded under CINUK can represent best practices of how cooperation between European and North American partners could develop. Thus, we can ensure that the observations collected thanks to pan-AOSS will be useful to better understand key issues connected to climate-driven changes to the terrestrial, coastal and near-shore marine environments in Inuit Nunangat, as well as the impacts on Inuit and community health and well-being.

5. Coordination initiatives to build a pan-AOSS on Arctic Ocean

The development of a structure for improved international coordination of Arctic oceanography, such as an Arctic GOOS (Global Ocean Observing System) Regional Alliance (GRA), has been recommended in various forums in recent years, including during the development of the Arctic Action Plan for the UN Ocean Decade and at various editions of the Arctic Observing Summit. A concept and framework for a Sustained Arctic Ocean Observing System was also developed in detail by the marine community in the past years (Lee et al. 2019).

In order to advance discussions and to develop a roadmap towards realisation of a structure for international coordination of ocean observation in the Arctic, a roundtable discussions meeting was held during the 2023 Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) in Vienna. The concrete outcome of this meeting was the establishment of a Task Team to design and lead a process to form an Arctic GRA. This Task Team engages a diverse range of stakeholders, including representatives of Arctic Indigenous and Local communities and organisations. Current composition of the Task Team and its term of reference are reported on the SAON web page (SAON, 2025).

The expected outcome of the Task Team should be a proposed design for a pan-Arctic ocean observing alliance (such as a GRA) that brings together all sustained ocean observing initiatives in the Arctic in a single entity or structure. In order to ensure the greatest possible inclusiveness and authority to this process, the Task Team working to design an Arctic Ocean regional Alliance (ArORA) has the full support and formal recognition of both SAON (Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks) and GOOS (Global Ocean Observing System).

The starting point of the Task Team's work is to recognize that existing GRAs such as US IOSS, EUROGOOS, CIOOS, already encompass elements of the Arctic Region and therefore the main

purpose of ArORA will be to complement existing regional Alliances, facilitating pan-arctic communication and coordination.

The future system will span the whole ocean-observing value chain, from the observations themselves to the benefits for the users. It will include all sustained ocean and sea ice observing activities in the Arctic (research, operational oceanography, monitoring, community based monitoring, etc.). The proposed design of the pan-Arctic observing alliance will be inclusive of the needs of different rights holders, stakeholders and actors, including Arctic Indigenous Peoples and other Arctic residents. A schematic view of who the ArORA would serve is reported in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - RA schematic of scopes and stakeholders ArORA should serve

The period 2023-2025 was mainly spent consolidating the discussion and expanding the Task Team, in particular involving representatives of Arctic populations and other relevant stakeholders. In particular, dedicated sessions were organized during the Arctic Science Summit Weeks of 2024 and 2025; at the last one, held in Boulder in March 2025, the Task Team presented its work to date on developing a formal proposal for a Regional Alliance and invited the community to further articulate the value/benefits of an Arctic Regional Alliance for Ocean Observing, based on the main themes

- 1) Participation and work to broaden input from diverse rights-holders and stakeholders,
- 2) Concerns and needs of Indigenous and coastal communities,
- 3) Structure - What form should the RA take?
- 4) Function - What useful services might the RA provide?
- 5) Governance What structure would be effective and appropriate?
- 6) Review and evolution - How do we build-in regular, community-driven assessment and RA evolution in response to feedback?

This action and initiative starts from the bottom and develops entirely within the coordination and governance framework of the Arctic scientific community. In parallel to it, a synergistic action has been promoted by the scientific community within the political framework of the G7. The Group of Seven (G7) is an intergovernmental organization composed of representatives from Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, the United Kingdom and the United States. The European Union is also a member. In 2016, the G7 Ministers agreed to take an ambitious approach to tackling ocean issues, and developed the Future of the Seas and Ocean Initiative (FSOI) with five main Action Areas, that also include Ocean observation and regional Observing Capacity (G7-FSOI, 2025). The working group meets annually to review common priorities and emerging issues, and to identify how the combined national actions of the G7 can advance global ambitions. The G7 FSOI work plan responds to priorities highlighted in the communiqués and statements of G7, in tables dedicated to Science and Technology. Since 2023 its priorities included one pushed by Japan and EU devoted to improve Arctic Ocean Observing (G7-FSOI, 2023). As stated on the FSOI web page objective of this priority is

Increase G7 activities and collaborations to enhance in-situ observation and data sharing in the Arctic, particularly through the use of research vessels to complement the OneArgo program, and to develop human resources to meet current and future needs for polar observing.

And planned activities for 2025 are:

Encourage the continued engagement of G7 experts in the Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance (ArORA) Task Team to develop a strategy, implementation plan, governance structure, and project office needs to implement ArORA as a sub-panel of SAON and in collaboration with GOOS, and to share this strategy with the G7 FSOI Working Group for consideration.

What is indicated for 2025 is in effect the outcome of two years of work and dialogue that the reference science community was able to develop with the Working Group and G7 system. An essential element of this dialogue has been the 1st International Workshop on Arctic Ocean Observation: Future Collaboration by Research Vessels and Icebreakers held in Tokyo November 2023, on the side the G7-FSOI 2023 annual meeting (JAMSTEC, 2023)

Thanks to the development of these two actions and especially to the synergy that has been created between them, the objective of building a sustainable pan-Arctic observation system for the Arctic Ocean and coastal areas seems to be on the right track. In particular, the interest of the G7 could be valuable in ensuring, in a stable form, the resources necessary to implement a coordinating office of ArORA.

6. Activities carried out within the frame of the project

6.1. With Asian Partners

Since the consortium preparation phase, the project has been seeking the best way to connect with the reference institutions of the Asian countries. During the proposal, NCPOR participated in the drafting of the plan, while later KOPRI, JAMSTEC and NIPR joined the efforts and discussions. This is mainly thanks to the great work of presentation and promotion that Arctic PASSION has carried out

since the early stages in all possible events and forums. Although the preparation of the project proposal was started in 2019, both the finalization of step 1 of the call (presentation of a 10-page document with the general idea) and then that of the preparation of the complete proposal (step 2) took place with the pandemic in full development. This has certainly created significant problems and weaknesses that have limited the project's ability to operate on the issues of cooperation with Asian partners at least until 2023. The geopolitical upheavals that occurred in 2022, the disruption with Russian partners has created a further obstacle, reducing the number of channels in which to meet and dialogue. Until 2022 we can say that only the occasion of the Arctic Science Summit Week had really been useful for that purpose.

In 2023, the situation changed decisively, and this is thanks to two important factors: (i) the active presence of Asian partners at the General Assemblies of the project (starting with the one in Baveno - Italy); (ii) the decisive start of the ArORA action and the dialogue and common effort both at SAON and GEOOS and in the more political environment of G7-FSOI.

The presence in those contexts of several experts actively involved in Arctic PASSION, representing their institutions and countries, creates a first strong line of dialogue and pushes the search for synergies. At the same time, cooperation and dialogue with the American action mirroring Arctic PASSION, RNA-CoObs, is also activated and strengthened.

The workshop organized in Tokyo in November 2023, sees a strong participation and contribution from Arctic PASSION to the discussion, especially with regard to "Addressing Knowledge Gaps and Future Research Collaboration" (JAMSTEC, 2023). At the 2024 ASSW, which hosts the biannual Arctic Observing Summit dedicated to starting the process of developing the ICARP ten-year plan, Arctic PASSION actively continues to promote and further advance this dialogue. Meanwhile, other events offer the opportunity to give greater strength and continuity to this effort, which as we have seen focuses mainly on the marine domain. The General Assembly of the RNA-CoObs action at the end of August 2024 certainly stands out: there, specific sessions see European, American and Asian partners dialogue together on this common goal.

The idea for a workshop to be held online was developed in the last months of 2024 and the first months of 2025 with the aim of addressing the topic of cooperation between European and Asian partners for a common effort towards a pan-AOSS. A first circular was distributed among potential participants in February 2025. The circular developed and distributed is reported in the Appendix. The program, based on two sessions of 3-4 hours to be held at a time suitable for the participation of both Europeans and Asians, should make it possible to

the FIRST DAY - share information on activities and collaborations in the Arctic and give elements about future plans and perspectives.

the SECOND DAY - focus discussion on challenges, barriers and possible instruments to overcome them. Address the issue of indigenous participation and also take time to summarize results and discuss next steps.

Unfortunately, so far it has not been possible to find a suitable date for adequate participation. It is planned to relaunch the same circular with a new series of windows focused on the period September-October 2025

Finally, coming to the ASSW 2025 held in Boulder in March 2025, we must point out how the development of the dialogue and the intense preceding activity has allowed us to organize several sessions in which to discuss and deepen the themes of cooperation and common effort of

Europeans, Asians and Americans towards a pan-AOSS. Among the many sessions that can be found in the program (available on the ASSW web page), we would like to highlight the following 2:

1 - we already mentioned the first one in section 4: it is going to be held in the afternoon of March 22, about the Pan-Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance; experts from AWI, BAS, UiT, UW, NPI, CNR will contribute for the project;

2 - the second one, restricted to invitations, co-organized with the American RNA-CoObs project, on the morning of March 24, on sharing our visions for a future Arctic observing system. In preparation for this session, all the invited participants were asked to present their personal idea and vision about the pan-AOSS. Starting from this material and from a synthesis of the ideas received, breakout panels addressed specific aspects, such as "linking/sharing observations across scales", "Discovery & interoperability of Arctic observing Data", "knowledge products" and others. The material collected in preparation for the meeting and the outcome of the discussion that will be reported in the minutes that are being prepared, will set the state of the art in the definition of a comprehensive plan for pan-AOSS. Hence, it is a starting point to leverage for the next steps.

6.2. With US and Canada project partners to fill gaps

The Arctic Passion project consortium includes 4 partners from North America, two from Canada and two from the United States. In addition, this consortium cooperated with several Indigenous Communities and a local community. Three of them come from Arctic territories of Alaska and Canada. In the case of the Canadian partners, a national matching funding has allowed AINA and Universities of Carleton and Ottawa to have specific resources linked to the project. This composition allows the project to concretely carry out some activities aimed at improving the integration of the observation system on the pan-Arctic scale, systematizing the skills, experiences and best practices acquired in Europe and North America. In section 4 we said how this strategy that we could define as small steps, with well-targeted and focused actions, is, in light of the current scenarios and funding tools available especially in North America, a winning strategy. The work was carried out within WP1 and WP4 and the deliverables of these WPs, in particular deliverable D1.8, D4.5 and D4.11 are referred to for details on the actions.

For the marine domain, a main action concerned the development of an Atlantic node of the Distributed Biological Observatory (DBO). During Arctic PASSION's lifetime, bi-annual meetings have been organized and succeeded in

- 1) establishing an organizational structure for the A-DBO including relevant institutions and science communities
- 2) formulating a vision of collaboration to optimize the observational capacity, with the ambition to improve harmonization on methods and data
- 3) involving a broader science community of active scientists including early careers to build and strengthen disciplinary and interdisciplinary networks and to facilitate discussions on science questions and the important features on which to follow up
- 4) actively contributing and promoting the establishment of a Pan Arctic DBO network involving the A-DBO, the Pacific DBO, but also two complementary DBOs north of Siberia and in the Baffin Bay/ Davis Strait region
- 5) developing a vision and ambition for the Pan-Arctic DBO

6) communicating the DBO-concept to a wider research community (Deliverable D1.8). An extensive description, with maps and link to a A-DBO Cruise Package is at disposal on the project webpage (<https://arcticpassion.eu/adbo/>).

As far as the terrestrial and partly the atmospheric domain is concerned, the main action concerned the strengthening and harmonization of measures on a network of ten representative monitoring sites across different ecosystems and permafrost zones, laying the foundation for long-term climate system studies. A key outcome was the collaborative identification of Priority Parameters. They encompass

- meteorological parameters (air temperature, air humidity, air pressure, wind velocity, wind direction, precipitation)
- energy balance and radiation (short wave incoming radiation, short wave outgoing radiation, long wave incoming radiation, long wave outgoing radiation, net radiation, UV-B, sensible heat flux, latent heat flux, soil heat flux)
- sub surface characteristics (permafrost/ground temperature, ground surface temperature, soil temperature, active layer thickness)
- snow characteristics (snow depth, snow density, snow temperature).

These parameters are of particular interest when studying the Shared Arctic Variables actions that are supported and driven by Arctic PASSION on wildfires, permafrost degradation and sea ice (Deliverable D1.8).

Cooperative activities involving European and Nord American partners (in particular Indigenous and local community) also were developed in the frame of WP4, the WP devoted to develop several services for specific needs. In the context of cooperation with territories and realities of North America, we can certainly underline

AS-1: Arctic Service 'Event Database of CBM Using Oral Histories, Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge'

AS-2: Pan-Arctic requirements-driven Permafrost Service (ALEX) AS-4: Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA) Service

For each of them, detailed information and links to reach and use/test them can be found on the project web page. Detailed descriptions can then be found in the WP4 deliverables.

6.3. With RNA CoObs

In section 4, the analysis of the Arctic research landscape in the United States and Canada led us to the conclusion that effective collaboration in a pan-AOSS perspective must start from the bottom, involving the scientific communities and the various partners in concrete actions that can be supported by current funding tools. However, it is certainly important to support this action with an action that sees the scientific community develop a comprehensive plan that can constitute a starting point for top-level discussions on multilateral tables and platforms (see section 7). The joint development of this plan guarantees to the institutions called to discuss, plan and decide that they can protect the interests of the respective national communities while maintaining their unity of purpose.

At the same time that the Arctic PASSION project materialized as a proposal and was funded, on the American side an American consortium prepared and submitted to the NSF a proposal for a project

that had very similar general objectives. The fact that this project was also successful in obtaining support and funding created the ideal situation to continue after 2021 also this second necessary piece of cooperation between Europe and North America towards an integrated and sustainable Arctic-scale observing system.

The Research Network Activities for Sustained Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change (RNA CoObs) project seeks to support the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) Roadmap for Arctic Observing & Data Systems (ROADS). Through meetings, collaborations, and partnerships with several entities, the project steps through the elements of ROADS, including the identification of Shared Arctic Variables tied to societal benefits, the capture of requirements for observing activities aimed at SAVs, and the design and adaptation of an information infrastructure. With a focus on the Pacific Arctic, the project is meant to help explore and demonstrate how an internationally coordinated roadmap for Arctic observation can be put into action. The vision and mission of RNA CoObs are to create meaningful relationships with Indigenous Peoples through the design of Arctic observing and observation systems and to build a community of practice around Arctic observing that serves societal needs and adds shared value for pressing decision-making needs (RNA CoObs web page, 2025).

In these 4 years, Arctic Passion and RNA CoObs have always maintained an intense dialogue and have jointly promoted the discussion on how to develop a well-integrated, sustainable observation system that is fair towards the Arctic populations, especially oriented towards their needs. Trying to create concrete examples of how the ROADS process designed by SAON can really be a useful tool to align priorities and interests of the different partners in Europe, North America and Asia, joint sessions have been organized regularly, mainly during ASSW and AOS events.

An area of effective collaboration has been that of the Shared Arctic Variables, where the two projects have carried out successful work on concrete cases. Arctic PASSION has focused on permafrost, wildfires, and sea ice, whereas RNA CoObs has devoted attention to salmon and Food security, harmful algal blooms [HABs] and wildfires. Following the ROADS guidelines, expert panels have been established. In the case of fires, a constant dialogue and sharing of the results as they are obtained, is maintained between the two expert panels established in Europe (under the impetus of FMI) and in America with the coordination of the University of Alaska. The synergic work of Arctic PASSION and RNA CoObs has allowed to better structure the ROADS process and to provide it with extensive documentation and guidelines that can be retrieved on the ROADS advisory panel web page (<https://roadsadvisorypanel.org/>).

The latest activity in chronological order has been a joint meeting organized by RNA CoObs and Arctic PASSION during the latest ASSW held in Boulder in March 2025. The strictly in-person and invitation-only meeting brought together about twenty experts from Europe, North America and Asia. The focus of this meeting was to share visions, ideas, and concepts for a future observing system. This vision included considerations about SAON ROADS, data systems and integration, equity, structure and governance, and sustainability. In order to better prepare the meeting and have a basis from which to start the discussion, each participant was asked to share in advance (i) a few sentences about lessons learned from implementing the SAON ROADS process and (ii) a single slide describing promising pathways they see to achieve their vision for a future Arctic observing network. Invited participants were encouraged to specify any aspects that might benefit from support and momentum from the International Polar Year and to think about their long-term

sustainability. Such specific aspects of data systems and integration, equity and structure-governance-sustainability were examined in depth inside breakout groups, and results of these analyses were reported and discussed in a final session. The outcomes of this meeting should be soon made available. They represent an important step along the road to developing a bottom-up proposal for the future pan-AOSS.

7. How/Where to continue dialogue for common efforts

In section 3.2, considering the status and perspective of cooperation with Asian partners, we listed several platforms suitable to promote dialogue on cooperative efforts towards an integrated Arctic observing system. We limited analysis to roundtables/platforms that were born in Asian countries on national pressure, and to the regional ones. In this section we enlarge that vision to platforms that have an intrinsically pan-Arctic character and so can bring together all partners/Institution interested to a pan-AOSS. Considering our specific objective, we focus on the most useful platforms and therefore avoid getting to list those that might seem more obvious, such as IASC, IASC WGs and WGs of the Arctic Council. These platforms are too general, useful for high-level endorsement, less for promoting concrete implementation actions. Taking into account this limitation, we can restrict our list to two relevant platforms. The first one, FARO, is very useful for the coordination and optimization of the logistic effort connected with a pan-AOSS. The second one, AsFF, is the most useful to secure the economic resources and the continuous interest of funding agencies.

FARO - As stated on its web site (<https://faro-arctic.org/>), the Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO) is a country membership organization that promotes dialogue on logistics and operational support for scientific research in the Arctic. It was started by 24 operators from 11 countries in August 1998. Today, FARO counts 21 member countries representing about 40 operators around the world. It is important to underline the country character of FARO.

FARO facilitates the exchange of information and the establishment of cooperation and development of new ideas among national operators of ships, stations and aircraft in the Arctic. FARO enables countries to optimize logistics and operational support for scientific research in the Arctic.

Therefore, in a pan-AOSS perspective, FARO is a discussion table that can make a decisive contribution to better use of research infrastructures. Unlike the first tables/platforms, CNAC, ArCAS, AERC, which are tools of the national policies and commitments of China and Japan, and regional organizations, FARO is a platform that covers and impacts the whole Arctic.

AsFF - Whereas FARO provides an important table on which to discuss the optimization and sustainability of operations, and therefore also what is needed to manage and maintain an efficient pan-Arctic observing system, the Arctic science Funders Forum provides the platform where to try and increase the coordination of the economic resources necessary to implement and then operate a pan-AOSS.

The Arctic Science Funders Forum is a multilateral discussion platform, originating from the Arctic Science Ministerial, for funders to initiate and investigate new and enhanced collaborative scientific activities in the Arctic.

Under the auspices of the second Arctic Science Ministerial, AsFF was officially established on 30

March 2020. The Forum is voluntary and open to representatives of the Arctic science funding programmes of the governments and of the six Arctic Indigenous Peoples Organisations that participated in ASM meetings. AsFF should

(i) work as a soft coordination body by facilitating information sharing for awareness of national and international calls for Arctic research projects, without creating additional administrative burden for the funding organisations.

(ii) Develop bilateral and multilateral research funding programmes and calls, in accordance with the values and objectives outlined in the Joint Statement of Ministers from the Arctic Science Ministerial.

(iii) Provide a venue for Forum participants to come together to consider “big ideas”, be forward-leaning, and overcome obstacles to achieving the goals of the ASM.

(iv) Serve as a means to communicate priorities, activities, and opportunities, thereby catalysing synergies and stimulating extra leverage of national funding. It also may help adapt and optimize funding calls (timing, priorities, requisites, etc.) from the parties, highlighting the international perspective.

This table is the most recent, and the one that was most negatively impacted first from the pandemic and then from the new geopolitical situation. Being an initiative promoted and supported at a political level, even after the end of the pandemic it struggled to take off. However, during the Norwegian chairmanship of the Arctic Council, it began to be structured and to develop the first initiatives. Their first action consisted in creating an overview of science calls and activities/platform for members to contact each other. AsFF is a fundamental element of the puzzle that we must compose to arrive at a pan-AOSS. Coordinated projects can be born on this table and different actors can join together and put resources for a specific effort/purpose.

The two platforms briefly illustrated above are the places designated to maintain and strengthen the dialogue between the various actors, making it possible to align and, where possible, adapt national and/or individual institution and funding agency objectives/ priorities to those needed to realize the challenging target of a pan-AOSS. But such an observing system certainly cannot be built in a single block; not by chance, it is considered a system federation (System of systems). The easiest is that these systems, pieces of the puzzle, are coagulating within single “domains” like marine, atmosphere, cryosphere, land. In the following section, we consider what is currently happening in the marine domain, thanks to the combined success of initiatives promoted by the reference community in both the political and scientific areas.

8. Conclusions

We are certainly pleased by what is reported in the previous sections, because it indicates that cooperation between European and non-European countries is no longer in the future, but it is a developing reality.

Concerning the marine domain, we were able to note in section 5 the determining role of Japan in giving impetus to the prioritization of ArORA in the context of the G7-FSOI.

Although the road is traced, and the journey is already well under way, it is still long and several

obstacles still need to be overcome. The main one is undoubtedly managing to involve the end users, the Arctic populations, and the economic world and governance at regional and local level. Moreover, the problem of ensuring the huge resources necessary to support the research vessels and in general the ground-segment of the observation system should not be underestimated. The search for the co-participation of the economic world in the long-term observation effort is yet another challenge. The fixed and mobile platforms that private stakeholders can offer are precious resources; if it is possible to involve and use them, they could bring us much closer to the objective of an observation that has the right spatial and temporal coverage at sustainable costs.

A less obvious challenge is found within the scientific community. The tendency of this community to organize and group itself according to disciplinary fields has always been, and continues to be, very strong. And this leads to the fact that in the development of an observation plan for the marine domain, the privileged field is that which involves the community of experts in oceanography and marine biology. But the geography of the Arctic, an ocean surrounded by land, gives a significant weight to both the atmosphere and the land surrounding the Arctic Ocean, by virtue of the influences and forces that they have on the marine environment (just think of how long the Arctic coast is and how much the fjord system weighs on it). It is important that these components are well integrated into the observation system, in a holistic approach.

This last consideration adds to other reflections that we can make on the weaknesses that still exist and, on the work, to be done. The lines of action that we can identify and recommend strengthening cooperation between European and other partners, to get closer to the goal of implementing a pan-AOSS, include:

- **strengthen cooperation between European non-Arctic states and Asian actors.** The reports in sections 2 and 3 demonstrate that cooperation between China, Japan and a good part of the European Arctic countries is quite good, especially at the bilateral level. But cooperation with institutes and agencies of non-Arctic countries is not as structured. A stronger cooperation with Asian partners can also help to make coordinated efforts in improving observing system over Arctic Ocean as well as arctic regions of North America.
- **promote a better balance in the contribution of Asian countries.** It is quite clear that while China and Japan are very far ahead in contributing to the effort for a common pan-AOSS, Korea and India (not to mention other potential Asian partners) are not yet as committed. Multilateral cooperation could stimulate actions adequate to the commitment level of different Institutions and useful for the target of a pan-AOSS.
- **making the level of development of pan-AOSS more homogeneous.** We have seen in section 5 that for the Marine domain the level of coordination and planning is very advanced. But we need to (i) even in the marine domain, ensure the multidisciplinary level adequate for an holistic approach, and (ii) make a progress similar to that assured by initiatives like ArORA also for the terrestrial domain.
- **fully develop the synergy between ground-based and spaceborne observing segments.** It is very clear that satellite observation is fundamental to building a pan-AOSS system truly capable of responding to all our needs. However, without adequate integration with the ground level both to acquire parameters not easily observable from space and to robustly validate the retrieval algorithms, the observation system would not really be able to respond to the needs of all users.

- *make the most of new technologies.* The observational and analysis/interpretation possibilities available today offer opportunities unimaginable 5-10 years ago. Greater cooperation and common effort is essential to exploit all the opportunities both in terms of environmental sustainability (footprint) of observations and to exponentially increase the amount of data provided in NRT. This latter being a fundamental step if we desire to improve modelling or to use better opportunities offered by AI.

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Appendix I-

Workshop First Circular

Towards a pan-AOSS: status of cooperation between EU and Asian partners in the frame of Arctic PASSION

Background

The key motivation behind Arctic PASSION is the co-creation and implementation of a sustained, accessible, coherent and integrated Arctic observing system, tuned to the diverse needs of users, ranging from local inhabitants to academia through to industry and decision-makers. The ‘Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems – pan-AOSS’ aims to overcome known flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving, and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge, by streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services, and by ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system for years to come.

Taking significant steps towards this ambitious goal requires active collaboration between all the subjects involved and interested, trying to harmonize and better exploit the assets that history of scientific collaboration between European institutions and Asian research institutions have ended up sedimenting. If we focus on the marine domain, a very important initiative has been launched in 2023 in the G7 FSOI context, on proposal of Japan and full convinced adhesion of all the other G7 members. This effort well connected with the initiative, also lunched in 2023, to promote an Arctic GEOSS Regional Alliance (GRA) involving other countries. The participation to these two initiatives/tables of several partners (including project coordinator), makes Arctic PASSION strongly involved, and a useful tool to implement some of the recommendations and ideas that both initiatives can bring out. This either during the final phase of the project, either through its legacy or further developments/continuation with EU support. In any case, the pan-AOSS is certainly not limited to the marine domain alone.

A workshop, addressing the issue of collaboration between European and Asian institutions with the multidisciplinary and co-creation perspective of Arctic PASSION, can be a useful step now that the project is coming to an end. The outcomes of such a workshop could provide important inputs to WP8 and to the work of synthesis and integration of the achieved results.

Implementation

The workshop will offer the chance to assess:

- i status of activities and collaborations in the Arctic and future perspectives both from the European and Asian partners
- ii what are the problems and challenges that a coherent and integrated effort to create an observation system in the Arctic has to face (focusing on the peculiar aspects of the EU-ASIA axis)
- iii having in mind how research is organized in Europe and in the different Asian countries, identifying possible instruments/solutions through which to overcome barriers, increase coherence, give a strong push to the sustainability of a pan-AOSS

iv how we can together promote the participation of indigenous communities in the development and operation of the observation system

To facilitate a large participation, reduce carbon footprint, and last but not list, to keep all participants involved at the same level, the workshop proposed should be an online meeting only.

About the date of the meeting we can put on the table four proposals:

Aprile 23-24 2025 (23-25 also a possibility)

Aprile 28-29, 2025 (29-30 also a possibility)

May 12-14, 2025 (two days untile May 16 also a possibility)

May 28-30, 2025

We will fix the final date on the base of preference of possible participants.

Despite the meeting will be focused on EU and ASIA participants, the issue of the time is till something to consider carefully, taking into account that in Springtime difference between European and Asian countries can range between 2.5 and 8 hours. So, we can make the proposal to start between 7 am UTC. Table below show the starting time at local time in different countries

Organizing the workshop on two days and not more of 4 hours per day, we should be able to ensure/facilitate everyone's attendance.

		Portugal, UK	Germany , Italy, France	Bulgaria, Poland, Finland	India	Cina	Korea and Japan
		(UTC+1) legal	(UTC+2) legal	(UTC+3) legak	(UTC+5. 5)	(UTC+8)	(UTC+9)
Start	7:00 UTC	08:00 LT	09:00 LT	10:00 LT	12:30 LT	15:00 LT	16:00 LT

Agenda could be organized in such a way to address all targets indicated above:

- **FIRST DAY**, share information on activities and collaborations in the Arctic and give elements about future plans and perspectives. Just to fix a temporal target we can ask to focus on what envisaged by each participant for IPY 2032. Depending on the level of participation we can found time to start discussion on challenges, barriers and possible instruments to overpass them.
- **SECOND DAY**, focus/continue discussion on challenges, barriers and possible instruments to overpass them. Address the issue of indigenous participation and also take time to summarize results and discuss next steps

If the workshop piques your interest, we would like your help with:

- 1) framing better the goals and topics it should address;
- 2) letting us know your preference among proposal for dates, also indicating possible conflicting events a/o meetings that could prevent your attendance. To this scope answer the poll at the link <https://terminplaner6.dfn.de/p/5f275c68ca40b79fb0d2387cfccc881b-1099059>.
- 3) being ambassadors for this initiative, spreading the message to anyone that might be interested.

For further information and indicate your interest to participate please refer to Vito Vitale (vito.vitale@cnr.it) and/or to Enrico Brugnoli (enrico.brugnoli@cnr.it)

